

Goddess Worship in the Gangaridai Era: An Exploration of Forgotten Histories and Cultural Continuities

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In the study of literature, particularly within the framework of cultural history, one often observes how the mirror of society, as represented in literature, reflects its deep-rooted beliefs, customs, and practices. A central aspect of this reflection is religion—an inextricable part of social consciousness. While much of Indian religious history is documented in ancient texts, Epics and Purāṇas, there are civilizational and religious practices which have been censored, erased, ignored and forgotten. One such forgotten civilization is that of the Gangaridai.

Winged Female Deity, Chandraketugarh, 2nd Century BCE. Berlin Ethnological Museum

Despite being mentioned by numerous foreign travellers and historians, the Gangaridai civilization has remained largely absent from India's documented historical narratives. This article aims to shed light on Mātrkā worship during the Gangaridai era, exploring how this ancient religious practice has left an indelible mark on Bengali religious consciousness, even as it has been overshadowed by other forms of religious expression.

Who Were the Gangaridai?

The term **Gangaridai** is familiar to those who have delved into the writings of Greco-Roman historians such as Megasthenes, Pliny the Elder, and Ptolemy. Megasthenes, a Greek ethnographer and explorer, described the Gangaridai as a powerful kingdom located in the eastern region of India. According to him, the king of Gangaridai possessed a formidable army consisting of 60,000 infantry, 1,000 cavalry, and 700 war elephants. The Roman historian Pliny also spoke of the valor and military might of this civilization, while the Roman poet Virgil mentioned them in his works. Ptolemy, the famous Greek geographer, recognized Gangaridai not just for its military prowess, but also for its thriving trade network. Despite such glowing accounts from the West, the civilization of Gangaridai finds no mention in the Indian epics or Purāṇas.

Tournament of Valour: Terracotta Plaque from Chandraketugarh, 2nd Century BCE. Present location is unknown.

The question arises—why is there such a stark absence of Gangaridai in Indian literary and mythological sources? Situated in what is now the eastern part of India and Bangladesh, it is plausible that the Gangaridai were considered an "alien" civilization in the largely Aryan-dominated narrative of ancient Indian history, which often focused on kingdoms closer to the political and cultural heartland of Aryavarta. Thus, the Gangaridai civilization, though flourishing and formidable, did not feature prominently in the traditional epic-historical discourse.

Archaeological Evidence: Chandraketugarh and the Excavations

The story of Gangaridai might have remained a myth or legend, confined to foreign narratives, if not for the archaeological excavations conducted in the mid-20th century in areas like **Chandraketugarh** in West Bengal's North 24 Parganas district. From 1957 to 1967, eight excavations were carried out in the region, unearthing valuable artifacts, idols, and structural remnants dating back to the 3rd century BCE. These discoveries brought to light the existence of an advanced civilization, which aligned with the descriptions provided by foreign historians like Megasthenes.

Game of Dice, Chandraketugarh terracotta. 2nd Century BCE. Present location is unknown.

'Mermaid' or water-nymph, Chandraketugarh, 2nd/3rd Century BCE. Present location is unknown. .

Female Nature Spirit or Yakṣī, Chandraketugarh. 2nd/3rd Century BCE, Present location Honolulu Academy of Arts

Chandraketugarh has yielded a wealth of archaeological material, including terracotta figurines, pottery, seals, and sculptures, many of which represent deities or religious figures. The most significant among these are the **Māṭṛkā idols**—representations of mother goddesses—suggesting that the worship of female deities was central to the religious life of the Gangaridai people. These Māṭṛkā figures, often found alongside Yakshis, Apsaras, and other divine entities, provide crucial insight into the religious consciousness of the region, which was deeply rooted in **goddess worship**.

Māṭṛkā Worship: A Reflection of Bengal's Religious Consciousness

Māṭṛkā worship, or the worship of mother goddesses, has long been a defining feature of Indian religious practices, especially in Bengal. The mother goddess, in various forms and manifestations, continues to hold a central place in the religious lives of Bengalis, from **Durgā Pūjā**, **Kālī Pūjā**, **Lakṣmī Pūjā**, **Jagaddhātrī Pūjā**, **Saraswatī Pūjā**, **Śītalā Pūjā**, **Manasā Pūjā**, **Ṣaṣṭhī Pūjā** and more. This deep connection to maternal deities can be traced back to antiquity, as evidenced by the **Māṭṛkā idols** unearthed at Chandraketugarh. These idols, which predate the more familiar Hindu pantheon of gods, offer a glimpse into a time when **Māṭṛkā worship** formed the cultural backbone of this region.

Let us now examine some of the key Māṭṛkā figures found at Chandraketugarh and their continued relevance in modern Bengali religious practices.

Daśāyudhā

Among the Mātrkā idols found at Chandraketugarh, the most prominent is **Daśāyudhā**, a goddess figure that could be a prototype of **Durgā**. Durgā, the ten-armed goddess who slays the buffalo demon Mahishasura, is the central deity of Bengal's most significant festival held every year during autumn, Durgā Pūjā. The **Daśāyudhā** figure found at Chandraketugarh bears striking similarities with Durgā iconography, the latter might have been influenced by the former. With her hair adorned with ten miniscule weapons (hence the nomenclature Daśāyudhā, or the ten-weaponed goddess) and surrounded by four companions, she might be a precursor to the present-day Durgā.

Left: Daśāyudhā, Chandraketugarh, now at West Bengal State Archaeological Museum, Behala, Kolkata.

Lakṣmī

The worship of **Lakṣmī**, the goddess of wealth and prosperity, is another prominent aspect of Bengali religious life. Lakṣmī Pūjā is observed with great fervor across Bengal, particularly in households where she is believed to ensure a bountiful harvest and prosperity. **GajaLakṣmī**, the form of Lakṣmī depicted with elephants, has been found in various parts of India, including Bengal. At Chandraketugarh, plaque of **GajaLakṣmī** was unearthed, suggesting that the worship of Lakṣmī in Bengal has ancient roots. The fact that **Lakṣmī Pūjā** continues to hold such importance in contemporary Bengali life speaks to the enduring nature of this ancient religious practice.

Right: Gaja-Lakṣmī, Chandraketugarh. Present location is unknown.

Ṣaṣṭhī

The goddess **Ṣaṣṭhī**, depicted as a mother holding a child, is yet another Mātṛkā figure that has persisted in Bengali religious consciousness. The worship of Ṣaṣṭhī, the goddess of fertility and protector of children, remains widespread in Bengal today. Whether it is **Jamai Ṣaṣṭhī**, **Oronno Ṣaṣṭhī**, or **Neel Ṣaṣṭhī**, the goddess is invoked for the well-being of children and families. At Chandraketugarh, multiple terracotta figures of a mother with her child have been found, reinforcing the idea that Ṣaṣṭhī worship is a practice that dates back thousands of years.

Archaic Ṣaṣṭhī, Chandraketugarh. Present location unknown. However, a similar plaque of proto- Ṣaṣṭhī is at Met Museum.

Dhānyamatsyā and Saraswatī

The connection between fish, rice, and Bengali identity is well known. Bengalis have long been associated with their love for **hilsa fish** and rice, a dietary staple that has become part of their cultural identity. The worship of **Saraswatī**, the goddess of learning, also holds a special place in Bengali society. Interestingly, an idol of **Dhānyamatsyā**, a goddess holding a pair of fishes whose hair is adorned with ears of paddy (hence this nomenclature is suggested), was found at Chandraketugarh. While not directly linked to Saraswatī, this image reflects the unique connection between food, prosperity, and wisdom in the Gangaridai civilization, which may have evolved into the Saraswatī Pūjā that Bengalis observe today.

Left: Dhānyamatsyā from Chandraketugarh 2nd Century BCE. Present Location: Santa Barbara Museum of Art.

Right: One-horned goddess or Ekānaṃśā from Chandraketugarh 2nd Century BCE. Now in Asian Museum of Art.

The Evolution of Mātṛkā Worship: From Gangaridai to Modern Bengal

The **Mātṛkā worship** of the Gangaridai civilization was deeply integrated into the fabric of society, with each goddess representing various aspects of life—prosperity, protection, fertility, and wisdom. However, over time, this ancient mother-goddess tradition was assimilated into the larger Hindu pantheon, and many of the Mātṛkās were subsumed under male gods like Śiva and Viṣṇu/Kṛṣṇa. For example, the **Ekānaṃśā** goddess, once a powerful one-horned female deity in the Gangaridai era, was later transformed into **Subhadṛā**, the sister of Kṛṣṇa, a process that might have already started in Chandraketugarh, and gradually lost her prominence as an independent goddess.

The worship of **Maa Kālī**, one of the most widely revered goddesses in Bengal today, can also be traced back to the **Balaka Mātṛkā** or **Bird Goddess**, an ancient form of the mother goddess found at Chandraketugarh the image of which is given in the beginning of this article. Professor Tamal Dasgupta has argued that Kālī's origins can be linked to this bird-like deity who was worshiped in antiquity.

Conclusion: Rediscovering the Lost Legacy of Gangaridai

The **Gangaridai civilization** remains largely forgotten in mainstream Indian history, its legacy relegated to the margins of historical discourse. Yet, the excavations at **Chandraketurgh** have provided invaluable insight into the rich religious and cultural life of this ancient people. Through the **Māṭṛkā idols** and other artifacts unearthed at the site, we can trace the evolution of Bengal's religious consciousness from early antiquity to the present day.

Although the religious traditions of the Gangaridai have been absorbed and transformed by later Hindu practices, their influence can still be seen in the continued worship of mother goddesses like **Durgā**, **Lakṣmī**, **Ṣaṣṭhī**, and **Kālī**. The **Māṭṛkā worship** of the Gangaridai era laid the foundations for the vibrant religious culture that characterizes Bengal today, even as its true origins have been obscured by time.

In rediscovering the lost legacy of **Gangaridai**, we not only reclaim a forgotten chapter of India's history but also gain a deeper understanding of the profound and enduring connection between **Bengal's religious consciousness** and the ancient practice of **Māṭṛkā worship**. The **mother goddesses** of Chandraketurgh may have been forgotten by mainstream historians, but they live on in the hearts and minds of millions of Bengalis, who continue to celebrate their power, protection, and grace in every aspect of life.

Celebratory Procession, Chandraketurgh, 2nd/3rd Century BCE. Present location is unknown

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